

The Evangelical Trends Of Awka Diocesan Synod Of The Anglican Communion, 1987-2011

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Introduction

The mission of the church is to proclaim to the world the profound mystery of God and especially, His loving care for each human person. Traditionally, the proclamation takes form in word and deed. The existing challenge for each generation of Christians is to discover over and over again throughout the centuries how this proclamation is to be accomplished in the light of contemporary realities of its age. The form or strategy continuously undergoes adaptation while the fundamental substance of belief remains unchanged. John cited in Udezo (2007) states that, “the substance of ancient doctrine of the deposit of faith is one thing but the way in which it is presented is another” (p. 36). This presentation of faith is the evangelical strategies of the church. The evangelical trend of the Awka diocesan synod of the Anglican Communion needs to be understood in the light of contemporary scholarship. This envisaged scholarship could be established through historical account of the evangelical trend in the diocese. The period 1987 – 2011 witnessed some landmark achievements and there is need to reduce ignorance associated with poor articulation of the evangelical trend in Awka diocese. The encouragement needed in the evangelical trend of the Awka diocesan synod of the Anglican Communion seems lacking due to lack of a creative criticism of the evangelical trend of the Awka diocesan synod.

The Synodical experience and choice of Synod themes in the Diocese of Awka underscores the emphasis on evangelism in the mission of the Church. In all ramifications, synod sessions provided the Diocese of Awka with fertile opportunities to evangelize, reflect on its mission focuses and strategies, engage in critical self-appraisal, and address issues in the light of its vision and mission. There is no gain saying the fact that a well informed Synod delegate would be well equipped for evangelism. On the strength of the above fact, the researcher is of the view that Awka Diocesan Synods have been very effective in the evangelistic agenda of the Church, and not only to be seen as a policy making meeting. For evangelism goes beyond vigils, crusades and prayer conventions. Thus, Anikwenwa (2002) characterized evangelism as holistic, unifying and Christ oriented. According to him, holistic evangelism is multi dimensional with spiritual and material aspects of the good news which need to be proclaimed together. No area of life should be left out of the evangelistic endeavour. The repentance and regeneration of the sinner should concern evangelism just as much as the betterment of his living conditions and general welfare. This research adopts the historical method of investigation and the principle means of data collection are oral interviews and the review of existing literatures.

Definition of Terms

This paper will define the core terms in this topic which are: Evangelical, Diocese, Synod, and Anglican Communion.

a. Evangelical

Evangelical which has to do with Evangelism is defined according to Hornby (2000) as wanting very much to persuade people to accept ones religious views and opinion. Evangelism in few words according to Udezo (2007) is, “to bring or to announce the *Euangelion*, the goodness” (p. 70). This according to chatfield (1998) is not merely for people’s conversion but for their caring and disciplining.

b. Diocese

This according to Mbachu (1997) is a territorial jurisdiction of a bishop; a geographical unit under the supervision of a bishop. Stating further he noted that a number of Archdeaconries or deaneries make a diocese. This is practiced in some Methodist, Roman Catholic and Anglican Churches.

c. Synod

The word, synod according to Oji (2007), is “from the Greek word, *synodos*, meaning assembly” (p. 117). Oji also defines it as a local or provincial assembly of Bishops and other Church officials meeting to resolve questions of discipline, administration and other Church matters.

According to Anikwenwa (2002), Synod is the most representative assembly of the Diocese in Anglican Communion, consisting of the House of Bishop, the house of Clergy, and the house of laity. Shriver (1993) defines synod as composing of clerical, and often lay delegates, being part of an Episcopal polity and which each church or province of the Anglican communion is governed.

Brief History of Awka Diocese; Anglican Communion

It is one of the Dioceses located in the Eastern part of Nigeria and it covers the geographical area occupied by Awka North, Awka south, Anaocha , Njikoka, Part of Dunukofia Local Government Areas as well as the Ugwuoba community in the present Oji River Local Government Area of Enugu State.

According to Nwude (2012), the Diocese of Awka came into being on the 9th March, 1987, when it was carved out of the then Diocese on the Niger under Bishop J.A Onyemelukwe. It was inaugurated on the same day by Archbishop Timothy O. Olufosoye at the then St. Faith’s Pro-Cathedral Awka. The Diocese at inception, comprised today’s Dioceses of Awka and Aguata until the latter was carved out on the 5th September, 2005
It is the 31st Diocese created in the church of Nigeria (Anglican Communion).

Sessions and Government of the Synod

The Diocesan constitution (1987), states that “the life of a synod shall be six years and shall terminate on the 31st day of October in the sixth year of the synod” (p. 28). Sessions of a synod shall hold at such times and such places as the Bishop, who is the president of the synod may appoint; communicating the date and venue to the members through the clerical synod secretary not less than twenty one days before the appointed date. The presence of the Bishop or his representative and one-fourth of the clergy and one – sixth of the lay representatives shall be the quorum for a meeting of the synod for the due exercise of its powers.

Themes of the Synod

Each synod session has a theme that constitutes the premise of group discussions, synod motions and sermons, and the conclusions thereof are presented in a communiqué for public consumption. According to Mgbemena (2012), the following synod themes were elaborately and prayerfully discussed within the year of this research review.

- 1987 - Discerning God’s will for His Church in Nigeria Today
- 1988 - The Challenges of Mission and Ministry for the People of God

- 1989 - The Christian and the Word of God.
- 1990 - Waiting in Prayer and Devotion: Preparing for the Decade of Evangelism

- 1991 - It Matters Committing Ourselves to the Sovereign Lord of the Earth

- 1992 - It Matters Mobilizing God's People for Effective Evangelism
- 1993 - Evangelism
- 1994 - The Challenges of Christian Stewardship
- 1995 - Christian Faith and our Traditional Culture
- 1996 - Sacraments: Means of Grace and Hope of Glory.
- 1997 - Vision 2000 and Beyond
- 1998 - Called to Full Humanity
- 1999 - Marching Forward Under God to the Third Millennium
- 2000 - Jesus Christ is the Same Yesterday, Today and Forever
- 2001 - A Caring Church in our Needy society
- 2002 - Our Common Future, Human Environment
- 2003 - Jesus went with them
- 2004 - Seek Ye First the Kingdom of God and His Righteousness
- 2005 - Where is Your Faith
- 2006 - Yours is the Kingdom, the Power and the Glory
- 2007 - God Reigns
- 2008 - The Mission of the Church: Unfinished Task
- 2009 - The Youth: Challenges and Prospects
- 2010 - God's Abundant Grace.
- 2011 - Great Commission: A Compassionate Church

A careful study of the synod Themes from 1987 – 2011 would clearly highlight the vision and efforts of the Diocese at nurturing a holistic evangelism in the society. She is concerned with public morality, public institution, facilities, and the quality of life of the people at large. It is on this basis that the president of the synod made the choice of themes to address local, national and international issues that are not in accordance with God's plan for mankind as contained in the scripture.

Functions of the Synod

Awka Diocesan constitution (1987) stipulates the functions of synod as follows:

1. The synod of the Diocese has the power to enact such laws, rules, regulations, policies, guidelines and resolutions and to take such other decisions for the administration, management and control of the affairs of the Diocese as shall be conformable with the Diocesan constitution.
2. The synod shall work for the advancement of Christian religion and education, promotion of religious and charitable purposes and provide the machinery for the smooth administration of the Diocese.
3. It shall appoint the Diocesan Council and such Boards and Committees as are prescribed by the constitution.
4. It may by resolution appoint other Boards, Committees, or other bodies as it deems necessary which shall consist of members of the synod and any other members that the Bishop or the Diocesan Board may deem fit in the circumstances.
5. Notwithstanding other provisions of these regulations, the synod has power from time to time to make regulations and issue guidelines and directives for the election of representatives to committees and other bodies in the Diocese.

The second function as stipulated above is geared towards evangelical agenda. This has to attack the generally accepted notion that synod is policy making meeting for administration of the church.

Hosting and the Impact of the Awka Diocesan Synod on the Host Communities

The Diocese maintains that nothing happens until it happens locally. This principle has guided the growth and development of the Diocese within these 25 years. This grass root approach has guided the rotation of synod venues, thereby bringing the evangelistic polity to the doorsteps of the faithful. Synod carries and creates avenues for evangelism in the host communities. The visit to the Traditional institutions and other prominent places, praying together and sharing views in common, worship and open air crusades are sure ways of spreading the gospel and, thereby, enabling the Church to grow and develop.

The host Parish Church is given at least one year notice for preparations. The publicity it attracts and the mobilization of resources of all sorts in various ways herald the much – expected great assembly of the people of God in the Church and in the homes of the Faithful. Mgbemena (2012) wrote that the following towns and Churches have hosted the Awka Diocesan Synod within her 25 years of existence.

1. St. Faith's Pro – Cathedral Church, Awka	-	1987	
2. Holy Trinity Church, Igboukwu	-	1988	
3. St. Peter's Church, Agulu	-	1989	
4. St. John's Church, Ekwulobia	-		1990
5. St. Mary's Church Ukpo	-	1991	
6. St. James Church, Enuguabo – Ufuma	-		1992
7. St. Faith's Pro – Cathedral Church, Awka	-	1993	
8. St. Thomas Church, Umuchu	-	1994	
9. Immanuel Church, Adazienu	-	1995	
10. St. John the Divine Church, Oko	-	1996	
11. Immanuel Church, Enugu – Ukwu	-	1997	
12. St. Augustine's Church, umunze	-	1998	
13. Immanuel Church Ezinifite – Aguata	-	1999	
14. St. Faith's Pro – Cathedral Awka	-	2000	
15. St. James Church, Nanka	-	2001	
16. St. John's Church, Nise	-	2002	
17. St. Marks Church, Ajalli	-	2003	
18. St. James Church, Uga	-	2004	
19. St. Peter's Church, Amawbia	-		2005
20. St. Matthew's Church, Nibo	-		2006
21. St. Peter's Church, Abagana	-		2007
22. St. Jude's Church, Adazi – Ani	-	2008	
23. St. Michael's Church, Nawfia	-	2009	
24. St. Peter's Church, Agulu	-	2010	
25. Cathedral Church of St. Faith, Awka	-		2011

Synods in these Churches have impacted positively in the areas of infrastructural development as they would in their bid to host the synod like to have a beautiful environment and facilitates to ensure comfort of the delegates. This motivated these Churches to rehabilitate and build Churches, vicarages and other facilities in their churches.

The Synod Evangelical Trend in the Diocese of Awka; 1987 - 2011

In 1987 when the Diocese was inaugurated, the new Diocese observed that the task ahead was enormous. Thus, the theme, Discerning God's will for His Church in Nigeria Today was chosen. Discerning the will of God and doing it

was thought very crucial at the beginning of the Diocese. It was reaffirmed that the Diocese would steadily seek God's will in prayer and worship and bear fruit as God's ambassadors.

The 1988 synod reaffirmed its commitment to the mission and ministry of the Church. It enjoined all the faithful to rise to the challenges. Hence the theme, the challenges of mission and ministry for the people of God. Udezo (2007) noted these challenges, which this synod had earlier alerted her members to rise to. They are classified as political which involves enormous increase in the number of refugees in the world, the pressing problem of human rights abuses, reconciliation in conflict affected areas and social cum economic challenges – such as vast urban slums, disparity in health care between the rich and the poor and great increase in religious and cultural pluralism in our localities.

The 1989 synod which deliberated on the theme “word of God” noted that the Church is the new humanity which God, in Christ, has constituted. Thus, in Christ, the Church lives out her history in the power of the Holy Spirit. The Church is entrusted with the ministry of interpreting the word of God and ensuring that it is effectively preached as she embarks on the mission of making disciples of all nations. This synod emphasized the correct interpretation of God's word for sound evangelism and discipleship. For distortion of the word of God is dangerous in the course of spreading the goodnews and in later years after this synod, Soroibe (2006) rightly observed that Pastors, in competition to win greater converts no longer interpret the word of God correctly, rather they give people what they want in order to retain them.

Nwankiti (2000) stated that, 1988 lambeth conference recognized that evangelism is the primary task given to the church and it, therefore asked each Diocese of the Anglican Communion, in Co-operation with other Christians to make the closing years of the last millennium a Decade of Evangelism, with a renewed and united emphasis on making Christ known to the people of His world. For this reason, the Diocese of Awka in her 1990 synod prepared the minds of her members to get ready through prayer and devotion, to move into the interiors of the Diocese and evangelize.

The synod of 1991 considered the fact that for Evangelism to be meaningful, Commitments is indispensable. Thus the theme, “It Matters Committing Ourselves to the Sovereign Lord of the Earth”. The synod acknowledged the fact that commitment to Christian virtues can only be meaningful if the faithful commit themselves first to the sovereign Lord of the Earth.

The synod of 1992 reflected on the importance of mobilizing Christians for effective evangelism. It discussed extensively what is involved in Evangelism. This synod, according to Oji (2007), held that “Evangelism involves, stewarding the material resources of creation; serving human beings without discrimination; witnessing to the truth as it is in Jesus and seeing that God's Justice is done in society” (p. 126).

The 1993 synod held in the Pro – Cathedral Church of the Diocese – the Diocesan Mother church discussed, the theme, “It matters: Harnessing the people of God for effective Evangelism”. This underscores the centrality of Evangelism in the Diocese of Awka and her synods. In exploring the theme, the synod deliberated extensively on the Diocesan evangelistic strategies, challenges and prospects. Anikwenwa (1993) noted that the synod is all about mobilizing, motivating and equipping the people for effective evangelism. Effective evangelism according to him, in a holistic perspective is a total evangelism which does not make evangelism the business of any one individual but of all members of the church in word and deed.

The 1994 synod deliberated on the challenges of Christian stewardship. The synod underscored the importance of stewardship in the mission and ministry of the church and urged the people of God to be holistic in stewardship. Stewardship to this synod is a matter of spirituality in the sense that possession, talents and money need to come under the Lordship of Jesus Christ. Anikwenwa (1994) described stewardship as holistic and not just about giving out time,

talents and possession as many people quickly conclude on hearing the word. But responsible Christian giving of lives and possession which are brought under Christ's leadership.

Another problem that faced the Diocese in the course of evangelism was the issue of tradition and culture. It became necessary for the Diocese to acknowledge that there are still some areas of conflict between the Christian faith and traditional culture. Such areas include burial rites, sacrifice, belief in reincarnation and oath – taking. Therefore, the 1995 synod deliberated extensively on Christian faith and our Traditional culture. This synod held that the Christian Faith is opposed to whatever aspects of the traditional culture that scandalizes the Christian conscience. On the other hand, upholds cultural values and practices that are in accordance with the teachings of the church.

The 1996 synod which discussed sacrament as a means of Grace and Hope of Glory; was relevant at that point in time, considering the erroneous teaching of the new generation churches on the sacrament. The intention of this synod according to was to enable the church rekindle the understanding of those who have been misled on the biblical posture of the sacrament. It also challenged the church to be alive to her responsibilities of teaching and dispensing the sacrament as charged by the Lord of the church.

The 1997 synod focused on the vision 2000 and beyond. The synod noted that vision 2000 and beyond called for effective evangelism in spite of challenges of all sort. It noted that the vision of the church should be the vision of what God has purposed to do, is doing and will be doing. This vision demands that the church should engage in a reconciliation ministry in the world to which both Evangelism and social concern are integral to church's Mission.

Also, the 1998 synod theme was a section one reflection of the 1998 lambeth conference which addressed the issue of called to full humanity. According to Nwankiti (2000), this section was set out to debate and reflect on a number of seemingly themes such as human rights and human dignity, human sexuality, environment, modern technology, euthanasia, international debt and economic justice. Carey (1991) commenting on this call to full humanity stated that;

We are living in a fragmented society whose most serious dislocation is between the human and Divine. The majority of our contemporaries believes in God but give him no real place in their lives; they pray to him yet fail to see His significance for human existence. We need to remind them and ourselves that to lose sight of the spiritual end of human destiny is to lose the point of humanity. It is one of those ironies that only with God can people be fully human, and only with the spiritual does the material make sense. (p. 28).

The Diocese of Awka in Communion with Canterbury and Lambeth brought this theme home for reflection in her synod.

The thought about the third millennium was characterized by predictions of the Second Advent. Some Prophets of doom predicted that the world will come to an end in the year 2000. The 1999 synod deliberated on marching forward under God to the Third Millennium and enjoined the faithful not to have any reason to believe the false predictions of the end of the world. Instead, they should be consistently mindful of the fact that the Father sets those dates and not for us to know. The synod encouraged Christians to ignore the false predictions and march on confidently under God, who is our shepherd, to the third millennium.

The year 2000 was a special year, as it ushered in the third millennium and the third time the synod was held at the number one Church of the diocese with the theme 'Jesus Christ as of yesterday, today and forever.' This synod discussed Jesus Christ as of Yesterday, Today and Forever. It reflected in the unfailing presence of God in the affairs of His people. It enjoined the faithful to be steadfast in their faith in season and out of season.

The 2001 synod discussed a caring church in our needy society. Onyemelukwe (1980) regretted the unfortunate thinking of the Church as a building, an institution; a place where God is worshipped and Gospel preached at regular or stated times. He defined the church as people, the family of God, God's people, the ordinary people – men, women, young men and women and children. Stott (2007) affirms that;

A caring Church is a Church whose fellowship is warm, welcoming and never marred by selfishness and jealousy. A church whose members love one another and bearing one another's burdens. A church which offers friendship to the loveless, support to the weak, and acceptance to those who are despised and rejected by society and in the church. (p. 181).

The synod enjoined the faithful to go back to their various parishes and localities to plan and execute on this crucial agenda.

The 2002 synod deliberated on human environment, having observed the global warming due to environmental pollution, wanton cutting down of trees, devastating effect of erosion and damaged atmosphere. Stott (1990) observe that;

Human beings may not have known it, or humbly acknowledged it but in all their research and resourcefulness... developing tools and technology, farming the land, digging for minerals, extracting fuels, damming rivers for hydroelectric power, harnessing atomic energy- all are fulfillment of God's primeval command. God has provided in the earth all the resources of food, shelter, water, clothing, energy and warmth which we need, and has given us dominion over the earth in which these resources have been stored. (p. 119).

The synod reminded the faithful that the whole creation requires integrity, if there is no integrity; the whole creation is adversely affected. The inventors, manufacturers and technologies were enjoined to not only consider the material profit but consider the after effect. The synod urged the church to reflect on this and speak out. Stott (1990) warned that "we should strenuously avoid all wastefulness...out of respect for the living environment" (p. 127).

Anikwenwa (2003) noted that;

Nigeria is fraught with many things that engender fear, frustration, discouragement and hopelessness. The mental agony and dehumanization through which our employable but unemployed young ones undergo, the ever increasing rate of corruption and its attendant ills; the growing rate of insecurity of lives and property. Inordinate quest for power and wealth, leading to the denial of victory to those who won elections and donation of success to those who failed; increase in mortality rate and low life expectancy of the citizenry, the agony of working without pay and retiring honorably from service without gratuity and/or pension, the emergence of dread diseases like Aids and Sars combine to make the future of many Nigerians gloomy and bleak. (p. 134).

And as Nigeria in 2003 experienced civilian political transition, it was important to know that without the presence of God, all our efforts would be completely futile. So the 2003 synod deliberated on the theme, Jesus went with them (Luke 7:6a and Luke 24:15b). The synod affirmed that a way forward is inviting the Lord Jesus to go with us.

Anikwenwa (2004) observed that:

The powers of fear and anxiety, lack of courage and clear identity; our dependency on man than God, and the influence of traditional religion on our Christian experience are among the factors dissuading Christians from their faith and life. It was and is still a common thing to hear and observe many attempts towards heathenisms and utter ungodliness among Christians of our day. Reports are rife of Christians reporting their brethren to heathen oracles to avenge alleged wrong doing against them, or settling disputes in shrines. Also, materials, childlessness, ill health and other social misfortunes were and are still factors that derail Christians from their faith. (p. 126).

Therefore 2004 synod reflected on seek ye first the kingdom of God and His righteousness. Seeking God and His Righteousness according to Oji (2010) means that Christians are under obligation to turn to God first in all things, fill their hearts with God's desires, take His character as their pattern, serve and obey Him in all things. The synod urged Christians to be absorbed in a diligent search for the kingdom of God and its righteousness.

2005 Synod which reflected on the theme, "where is your faith" enjoined the faithful to have implicit faith and confidence in God. The faith must work effectively and efficiently through love and sacrifice. The faith must also overcome doubt.

The 2006 synod continued to underscore the fact that God's pre-eminence is permanent and His leadership is forever and above all. Hence the theme, "Yours is the Kingdom, the Power and the Glory". While the 2007 theme, "God reigns" was an essential continuum of the previous theme. The synod upheld that God reigns absolutely in season and out of season, and enjoined all the faithful to allow God reign in their lives and activities, always bearing in mind that to Him belong the kingdom, the power and Glory forever.

The synod of 2008 re-affirmed and highlighted the Church of Christ as an institutionalized agent with the mandate towards the redemption of the created order, noting that the implication of the mandate is multidimensional, enormous and quite challenging. It is therefore a continuum that runs while the ages last. This synod which its theme was, "the mission of the church: Unfinished Task", proposes that all hands should be on deck and that the people of the mandate should neither wax cold nor grow weary or fainthearted in the face of the daunting task.

The 2009 synod deliberations were made on the challenges and opportunities of youth participation in the evangelistic stride of the Diocese. Anikwenwa (2009) noted that;

Reawakening of attention on the Youth, in recent times by the Anglican Church was engendered by the need to reposition them in the mission and ministry of the Church, and to enable them to overcome the social, economic, political and technological challenges of the time. (p.116).

This synod theme – "The Youth: Challenges and Opportunities", was primarily intended to enable the Diocese examine her scheme and programs for youth evangelism and their involvement in the evangelistic pursuit of the Diocese. The synod therefore emphasized that the Church must continue to strive to enable the youth overcome their challenges and make best of the opportunities available to them to grow in the faith and, also, serve the society as responsible and productive citizens.

The year 2010 marked the transition from the episcopate of Archbishop Maxwell Anikwenwa to the episcopate of the second Bishop, Alexander Ibezim. Hence 2010 synod was the conclusion of Archbishop Anikwenwa's presidency in Awka Diocese synod. Anikwenwa (2010) therefore noted that;

Throughout Paul's epistles, he starts with the Grace and ends up with it. It is not, therefore out of place if I conclude my synod like Paul. I began with Grace some 24 years ago...It is an unmerited favour – the grace and now to Him be the glory. Amen. (p. 104).

This synod concluded by saying aloud that the Religion of the Bible is a religion of grace or it is nothing – no Grace, no Gospel.

The 2011 synod at the Cathedral Church of the Diocese with the theme, "the Great Commission: Compassionate Church" was the first presidency of the second Bishop of the Diocese, Bishop Alexander Ibezim. Thus, Ibezim (2011) stated that;

As this is the first year of our Episcopate, I personally feel we should dwell on things that would engage our minds on the first things of our Christian calling... it seeks to remind us, and equally lead us to rediscover the original mandate of the Church; and to reinvent the means, ways and methods of fulfilling the same in our needy world today. (p. 161).

The synod's cumulative emphasis of the Great Commission is on evangelism and social responsibility squarely placed on the Church as Christ representative on earth.

Conclusion

The neglect of synod as a tool of evangelism is really unacceptable. It is unfair to attribute only preaching, visitation to the sick, crusade, prayer convention to Evangelism, while synod is taken to mean policy making meeting. Any evangelical achievement of the Diocese of Awka, without synod experiences and contributions, is not a fact. Therefore, Synod is evangelical. Notwithstanding the positive impact in the areas of infrastructural development on the host churches and communities, this research does not support the enormous financial responsibility of the synod

on the host church and community. The synod in the Diocese of Awka is capital intensive in the hosting and launching for Diocesan Projects, making the synod venues available only to big Churches neglecting the small churches. The researcher recommends that Synod venues should be shifted to every Church irrespective of their hosting capabilities as a result of money. The Diocese should see beyond the financial implication and gains but the evangelical aspect the synod carries. The lodging of the delegates which has over the years created a burden to the members of the host Church should be done away with, for the good access road and the close vicinity of the areas within the Diocese can afford the delegates to attend the synod from their homes. The diocese can also use synod to attract some developments in her non viable churches by taking the delegates to those areas and raise fund to develop them.

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